

Non-isothermal degradation and kinetic parameters of some Schiff base complexes

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Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been synthesized with the Schiff bases prepared by condensation of 2-aminopyridine with furfuraldehyde (FAP)/ethyl methyl ketone (EMKAP), 2-aminophenol with furfuraldehyde (FAPh)/salicylaldehyde (SAPh) and ethyl methyl ketone (EMKAPh). The molecular formula of the complexes are $[\text{M}(\text{FAP})_2]\cdot\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1), $[\text{M}(\text{EMKAP})_2]\cdot\text{Cl}_2$ (2), $[\text{M}(\text{FAPh})\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3), $[\text{M}(\text{SAPh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) and $[\text{M}(\text{EMKAPh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5). The TG data of decomposition of the complexes have been analysed for the kinetic parameters employing Coats-Redfern and Piloyan-Novikova non-isothermal methods. The order of thermal stabilities have been evaluated.

Schiff bases are known for their biological, industrial and analytical importance. There are reports¹ on the synthesis of transition and inner-transition metal complexes of Schiff bases involving salicylaldehyde and amines, amino acids and aminophenols, but no report is available on the solid state kinetic studies of such complexes.

The present communication deals with the synthesis, thermal degradation and evaluation of kinetic parameters of complexes of bivalent Co, Ni and Cu ions with Schiff bases, viz. furfurylidene-2-aminopyridine (FAP), ethyl methyl ketone-2-aminopyridine (EMKAP), furfurylidene-2-aminophenol (FAPh), salicylidene-2-aminophenol (SAPh), ethyl methyl ketone-2-aminophenol (EMKAPh).

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physicochemical data of the ligands and complexes are presented in Table 1. The conductivity

data of complexes (in 10^{-3} M methanol) show 1-2 electrolytic nature for FAP, EMKAP and EMKAPh metal complexes while FAPh and SAPh complexes show the non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectrum of the FAP-ligand shows a strong band at 1630 cm^{-1} (C=N) which is shifted to lower frequency region (1610 cm^{-1}) in the complex indicating the participation of azomethine group in chelation. A medium intensity ligand band is observed at 1125 cm^{-1} (C-O-C of furan ring). On coordination of ring oxygen with the metal ion, the band position of C-O-C group is shifted² to 1158 cm^{-1} . The new bands at 515 and 425 cm^{-1} in the metal complex have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ mode, respectively.

The EMKAP-ligand shows a band at 1623 cm^{-1} (C=N), which on complexation is shifted to lower frequency region (1608 cm^{-1}), suggesting the participation of azomethine group on complexation. Pyridine shows bands at 3130 , 1480 and 1040 cm^{-1} . These bands show positive shift by $15-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complex, suggesting the participation of pyridinyl nitrogen on complexation³. The band at 430 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ mode.

The ligand FAPh exhibits bands at 3450 and 1391 cm^{-1} due to phenolic OH stretch and deformation respectively. These bands are absent in the spectra of the complex. An intense ligand band at 1272 cm^{-1} (phenolic C-O) is shifted to higher frequency (1276 cm^{-1}) in the complex. These suggest the deprotonation of the phenolic OH after its chelation with the metal ion⁴. The ligand band at 1666 cm^{-1} (C=N) is shifted to lower frequency (1617 cm^{-1}) in the complex, indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen. A medium intensity ligand band at 1220 cm^{-1} (C-O-C of furan ring) is shifted to lower frequency side

Table 1 Analytical and magnetic data of the complexes*

Compd (no)*	Colour	M p °C	μ_{eff}
FAP	Black	80	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1)	Brown	95	Diamag
EMKAP	Brown	90	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (2)	Blue	210	4.10
FAPh	Brown	95	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3)	Brown	220	5.06
SAPh	Brown	90	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4)	Brown	210	3.03
EMKAPh	Brown	90	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot \text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5)	Brown	220	1.89

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

(1190 cm^{-1}) on coordination with ring oxygen. The new bands at 470 and 430 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations in the complexes.

The SAPH ligand band at 1629 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower frequency (1619 cm^{-1}) on coordination, suggesting the participation of azomethine nitrogen. The ligand bands at 3407 and 1364 cm^{-1} due to the stretching and deformation vibrations of phenolic OH group, are absent in the spectra of the complex, suggesting deprotonation of the phenolic OH. An intense ligand band at 1274 cm^{-1} (phenolic C–O) is shifted to higher frequency (1278 cm^{-1}) in the complex, suggesting the participation of phenolic oxygen on coordination. The new bands at 520 and 415 cm^{-1} are due to the $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ mode in the complex.

EMKAPh ligand band at 1588 cm^{-1} (C=N) is shifted to lower frequency region (by 10–20 cm^{-1}) on complexation suggesting the participation of azomethine nitrogen on coordination. The phenolic bands at 1389 (O–H) and 1272 cm^{-1} (C–O) of the ligand is shifted towards higher frequency side by 25–30 cm^{-1} , which suggests the participation of protonated phenolic group on complexation. The new bands at 550 and 420 cm^{-1} in the complex are due to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ modes, respectively.

On the basis of magnetic moment value (Table 1) a square-planar geometry for compounds **1** and **5**, tetrahedral geometry for compound **2** and octahedral geometry for compounds **3** and **4** are suggested.

Thermal studies :

$[\text{Ni}(\text{FAP})_2].\text{Cl}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) : A careful analysis of thermogram indicates that complex is stable upto 60°. Elimination of two lattice water molecules has been observed on raising the temperature upto 150° (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 8.00/7.03). Above 150°, a gradual weight-loss continues upto 400° which corresponds to the decomposition of the Schiff base and chloride moiety from the metal chelate. An inflection in the curve between the temperature region 460–630° shows a rapid loss in weight (degradation of remaining part of the ligand). A horizontal zone beyond 630° suggests the formation of an ultimate product, which in oxygenated atmosphere to be an oxide of nickel.

$[\text{Co}(\text{EMKAP})_2].\text{Cl}_2$ (**2**) : TG curve shows that there is no weight-loss upto 200° indicating the absence of lattice or coordinated water in the complex. A gradual increase in temperature above 200° has been accompanied by loss in weight upto 300°. It indicates part decomposition of ligand moiety (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 17.00/16.67). The remaining part of the ligand breaks at 300–600°. A horizontal thermal curve has been observed after 600°. This constant weight region corresponds to cobalt oxide, the final pyrolysis product.

$[\text{Co}(\text{FAPh}), \text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) : The TGA curve indicates that the decomposition starts at 60°. The lattice water comes out at 60–120° (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 10.00/9.25). This weight-loss corresponds to two molecules of lattice water. On increasing the temperature upto 150° the curve shows a weight-loss corresponding to two coordinated water molecules. Above 423° a gradual weight-loss occurs upto 350°. This indicates the decomposition of ligands moiety in two steps. The weight-loss observed at 220° corresponds to one molecule of chloride ion (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 9.00/9.12). Above 220° an inflection occurs in the curve and loss in weight progresses upto 350°. After 350°, the curve shows the continuous loss in weight due to remaining ligand parts. A horizontal thermal curve has been observed after 570°, suggesting the formation of an ultimate product cobalt oxide.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{SAPh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**4**) : The TGA curve shows that the lattice water comes out at 70–110° (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 10.00/10.06) (weight-loss corresponds to two molecules of water). A further loss in weight corresponding to three coordinated water molecules occurs on raising the temperature upto 240° (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 15.00/15.01). The thermal degradation of the Schiff base from the metal chelate occurs mainly in two steps, at 240–320° and 320–550° where the pyrolysis curve shows the continuous loss of ligand. Almost horizontal thermal curve has been observed after 550°. The percentage weight of the residue in this zone (i.e. 24.00%) may correspond to a mixture of nickel oxide and some ashes (uncharred part of ligand) as ultimate pyrolysis product.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{EMKAPh})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2].\text{Cl}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**5**) : The complex starts decomposing at 60°. Elimination of two lattice molecules has been observed on increasing the temperature upto 210° (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 9.00/9.74). A further loss in weight has been observed upto 290°, which corresponds to two molecules of coordinated water (% wt.-loss, obs./calc. : 17.00/19.48). The thermal degradation of the dehydrated metal chelate begins above 290°. A constant weight curve has been observed after 450°. The remaining percentage weight (20.00/19.35) corresponds to metal oxide as the final product.

Kinetic parameters for thermal decomposition : The fractional weight-loss (α) and the corresponding $(1-\alpha)^n$ have been calculated from TG curves at different temperatures, where n depends upon the reaction model and $\alpha = (w_t - w_f)/(w_o - w_f)$. The T vs $(1-\alpha)$ curves constructed on the basis of TG data for all the five complexes, are more or less of the same pattern. The decomposition reaction for the loss of Schiff base moiety from the complexes was subjected to non-isothermal kinetic studies. The weighted

least-squares method (LSM) was used for obtaining best-fit linear plots by applying the data to various equations and thus the kinetic parameters were evaluated. The values of slope, intercept and energy of activation were obtained from plots. The value of frequency factor (Z) was evaluated using eqn. (1) for P-N and C-R methods. The entropy of activation was calculated using eqn. (2),

$$\text{Intercept} = \log (ZR/\beta E) \quad (1)$$

$$Z = k T_m/h \exp (\Delta S^*/R) \quad (2)$$

where k is the Boltzman constant, h the Planck's constant, β the rate of heating, R the molar gas constant and T_m the peak temperature. The value of E , Z and S^* are given in Table 2. The mechanism involved in decomposition is random nucleation and apparent order of reaction is one.

Table 2. Thermal kinetic parameters of the complexes

Compd no.*	Eqn due to	Decomp. stage/temp (°C)	E kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹	ΔS^* kJ mol ⁻¹
1	P-N	1st/190	9.57	99.44	-210.36
			4.78	177.35	-205.44
	C-R	2nd/590	76.58	404.57	-203.87
			88.07	775.18	-198.46
2	P-N	1st/260	19.14	153.03	-207.57
			38.29	273.33	-203.13
	C-R	2nd/480	38.29	317.59	-204.75
			38.29	217.17	-207.91
3	P-N	1st/220	38.29	323.98	-201.06
			26.80	325.98	-201.00
	C-R	2nd/450	19.14	148.51	-210.73
			19.14	160.87	-210.04
4	P-N	1st/230	19.14	217.16	-204.56
			19.14	217.15	-204.56
	C-R	2nd/480	23.90	251.41	-206.69
			47.86	339.91	-204.18
5	P-N	1st/180	9.57	181.20	-205.19
			7.65	226.41	-203.34
	C-R	2nd/400	3.82	84.84	-214.79
			34.46	146.35	-210.26

*Same as in Table 1

The values of kinetic parameters have been calculated by C-R and P-N methods. Theoretically with decreasing the value of E^* the value of Z increases and the higher value of activation energy suggests the higher stability. However, there lies some inherent physical and chemical factors which may cause a change or deviation in this trend. Higher value of E^* (activation energy) and lower values of Z (frequency factor) favour the reaction to

proceed slower than normal. In present studies, the numerical values of activation energy E^* , frequency factor (Z) and entropy of activation altogether indicate about the smoothness of the feasibility and reaction rate of the initial reactants and intermolecular stage compounds

The negative values for entropy of activation indicates that the activated complexes have a more ordered or more rigid structure than the reactants or intermediate and the reactions are slower than normal. Quantitatively slight change in the entropies S^* of the compounds (than E^*) can not be set a reaction governing factor.

Kinetic parameters for these compounds have been determined individually at the first and second decomposition stages. Usually the first decomposition temperature lie in the range 180–260° and the second one at 450–590°. The order to thermal stability of compounds comes to be $2 > 4 > 3 > 1 > 5$ (on the basis of first decomposition stage) and $1 > 2 = 4 > 3 > 5$ (on the basis of second decomposition stage). The order of stability of the compounds on the basis of the values of activation energy can be set as $1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5$ (for first step) and $1 > 4 > 5 > 2 > 3$ (for second step). The variation in the trend might be interpreted to be due to some intermolecular interactions (structural as well as electronic) occurring therein. These are besides several experimental factors⁵.

Experimental

The ligands furfurylidene-2-aminopyridine, ethyl methyl ketone-2-aminopyridine, furfurylidene-2-aminophenol and salicylidene-2-aminophenol were synthesized by adding a methanolic solution of the appropriate amine to a methanolic solution of respective aldehyde/ketone in 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing the resulting mixture on a water-bath for 4–6 h. The coloured product was crystallized from diethyl ether. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC.

The metal complexes were synthesized by adding a methanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt $MCl_2 \cdot xH_2O$ (0.01 mol) to a methanolic solution of Schiff bases FAP/EMKAP in 1 : 2 ratio or FAPh/SAPh/EMKAPh in 1 : 1 ratio, and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4–6 h. The refluxate was kept overnight and the resulting solid was washed with methanol and ether. The metal complexes were dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator.

M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal CL-0301 apparatus. TGA and IR spectra were recorded at R.S.I.C., Nagpur.

References

1. J. Straszko, M. Olszak – Humienik and J. Mozejko, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1997, **292**, 145; P. Mu, R. Wang and L. Zhao, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1997, **296**, 129; M. K. M. Nair and P. K. Radhakrishnan, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1997, **292**, 115; R. Seera, J. Sempere and R. Nomen, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1998, **316**, 37; C. K. Hsu, J. S. Lee and C. W. Huang, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1998, **51**, 295.
2. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1986; H. K. Duggal and B. V. Agarwala, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, **4**, 1; B. B. Mahapatra, M. K. Raval, A. K. Behera and A. K. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **72**, 161.
3. B. Singh, P. L. Maurya, B. V. Agarwala and A. K. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 29.
4. N. S. Biradar, M. A. Pujar and V. R. Marathe, *Indian J. Chem.*; 1971, **9**, 712; P. B. Chakrawarti and P. Khanna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 112; M. L. Dhar, V. K. Gupta and O. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 739.
5. P. Chourasia, K. K. Suryesh and A. P. Mishra, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1993, **105**, 173; A. P. Mishra, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 1995, **65**, 395; *J. Int. Acad. Phys. Sci.*, 1997, **73**; A. P. Mishra, V. Vyas and J. D. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 927.